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Health Literacy and Colorectal Cancer Screening

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Abstract

Health literacy (HL) is the ability to receive, process, and interpret health information to make decisions regarding their care. According to studies, Inadequate HL has been linked to negative health outcomes, including a lack of health information, poor mental and physical health performance, poor management of chronic diseases such as cancer. Colorectal cancers (CRC), which rank third among the maximum, not unusual place styles of most cancers after lung and breast most cancers are the second one maximum common purpose of most cancers' deaths with 862 000 deaths. The incidence of CRC during life ranges between 2.4% and 5%, and positive risk factors for someone has a growth in the incidence of CRC. If was diagnosed at an early stage, CRC is a relatively treatable disease. If was diagnosed at an early stage, CRC is a relatively treatable disease The major motive of CRC screenings is to locate colorectal pathologies withinside the premalignant period, to lessen the frequency of invasive cancer, and for that reason morbidity and mortality rates, to prevent complicated remedies and to lessen fitness expenditures. Without a good understanding of information, health care will be difficult or impossible to make informed decisions that will lead to good health outcomes for herself and her family. With these Characteristic of measuring HL can be useful and necessary to be aware of and design special interventions to increase it, the possibility of Avoid the risks of limited literacy, as people with lower HL are more likely to assess their health as poor even after matching age, gender, race, and indicators of economic deprivation. Numerous articles have been published on correlation between CRC and HL; however, in the area of CRC Screening and benefiting from health literacy, a review might be helpful.

Keywords: Health literacy, Colorectal Cancers, Screening

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Introduction:

Health literacy (HL) is the ability to receive, process, and interpret health information to make decisions regarding their care.[1] Since the 1990s, the notion of HL has gotten a lot of attention. Even though the phrase was coined in 1974, it was recommended as a critical component of health promotion until 1997.[2] HL was included in the World Health Organization's (WHO) Health Promotion Glossary, with the following definition: Health literacy refers to the social and cognitive skills which determine an individual's motivation and ability to gain access to, understand, and use information in ways that promote and maintain good health.[3] It includes listening, reading, analyzing, and making decisions in the context of health. According to studies, Inadequate HL has been linked to negative health outcomes, including a lack of health information, poor mental and physical health performance, poor management over chronic diseases such as cancer, high hospitalization rates, high healthcare costs, and low medication adherence.[4] [5]

Cancer is a collection of complicated diseases that affects and kills millions of people throughout the world, and it has been the topic of intense investigation in both pathophysiology and therapy.[6] It is a group of disorders defined by uncontrolled cell proliferation that can penetrate and encroach on other body tissues. It is the second most common cause of death.[7] Colorectal cancers (CRC), which rank third among the maximum, not unusual place styles of most cancers after lung and breast most cancers are the second one maximum common purpose of most cancers' deaths with 862 000 deaths.[8] The incidence of CRC will increase after age 40–50. Of CRC cases, 90% are diagnosed in people above the age of 50, and this rate rises as much as 10% in men and 15% in women over 80 years of age. The incidence of CRC during life ranges between 2.4% and 5%, and positive risk factors for someone has a growth in the incidence of CRC. If was diagnosed at an early stage, CRC is a relatively treatable disease.[9] If was diagnosed at an early stage, CRC is a relatively treatable disease The major motive of CRC screenings is to locate colorectal pathologies withinside the premalignant period, to lessen the frequency of invasive cancer, and for that reason morbidity and mortality rates, to prevent complicated remedies and to lessen fitness expenditures.[10]

Participation rates for CRC screenings (figure 1) vary substantially from one program to another. The occurrence of CRC screening participation said to differ from 1.5% to 84.9% in worldwide studies.[11] [12] [13] It has been said that on a account of inadequate information of CRC signs and symptoms and threat factors of CRC, and insufficient awareness of screening tests, participation in CRC screenings is low, and that this situation has turn out to be extra crucial due to inadequate records and steerage provided with the aid of using healthcare professionals, and inadequate HL levels. [14] [15] [16] The role of health literacy in understanding harms, potential benefits, options and uncertainties related to most cancers screening is an undeniable fact.[17]

Patients with poor health literacy have a difficult time understanding material that contains unfamiliar terms or concepts. They frequently misunderstand cancer control phrases like screening, therapeutic, anatomical terms, diagnostic terms, and concepts including cure, lesion, and tumor.[18] HL is considered an important element to engage in health promotion and prevention activities for herself and her family. Without a good understanding of information, health care will be difficult or impossible to make informed decisions that will lead to good health outcomes for herself and her family. With these Characteristic of measuring HL can be useful and necessary to be aware of and design special interventions to increase it, the possibility of Avoid the risks of limited literacy, as people with lower HL are more likely to assess their health as poor even after matching age, gender, race, and indicators of economic deprivation.[19] Numerous articles have been published on correlation between CRC and HL; however, in the area of CRC Screening and benefiting from health literacy, a review might be helpful.

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Figure:1

Materials and Methods

This review covered the period between 1 January 1992 and 1 April 2022. Databases searched included: PubMed, Scopus, MSRT, Google Scholar, scientific SID, and BioMedCentral. We used the specified keywords to search and extract valid English articles from reliable electronic sources and by examining the complete texts of these articles, the resulting data as Described were categorized.

We searched Health literacy (in titles) and Colorectal cancers screening (in the titles and abstracts) as keywords in this study. Unrelated and duplicate items were removed. In the next step, All the remaining articles were reviewed and after removing the irrelevant items, the results related to the selected articles in the final stage were handwritten and reviewed.

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Results:

In several studies, a positive relation has been proven between the low HL and limited facts about cancer, and coffee most cancers screening rates.[20] [21]

Pancar et al. reported that Participation in CRC screenings was low, and people with a high HL stage were much more likely not to take part in CRC screenings. Working status, knowledge and consciousness levels affected the participation to CRC screenings. they claimed that To inspire humans to take part in screenings and to enhance their HL, consciousness-elevating tries for goal corporations should be increased.[22]

Another study reveled that HL may also play a function in shaping CRC screening adherence amongst low-income Hispanics. they advised that researchers should keep investigating how sociocultural factors impact screening adherence amongst Hispanics, using large and extra geographically numerous samples.[23]

White et al. illustrated that Low literacy was related to a reduced chance of using maximum preventive health measures below examine for adults elderly 65 and older and the connection between HL and preventive health practices various extensively by grownup age group.[24]

One study on African-Americans reveled that adequate HL of individuals might also additionally account for flat responses in negative attitudes. Further studies in people with limited HL is recommended. Moreover, extra schooling approximately self-relevance of most cancers hazard is requisite to growth cancer awareness in African-Americans.[25] Patients with limited literacy competencies are much less in all likelihood to be informed of CRC screening in comparison to adequate HL patients. Primary care companies should make certain patients' understanding of CRC screening while discussing screening options. Further studies is wanted to decide if instructing low HL patients approximately CRC screening can growth screening rates.[26]

A current study established that frequent publicity to CRC screening statistics results in considerably more screening participation. Sources of screening information included information reports, advertisements backed by the Screen for Life marketing campaign backed by the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), the American Cancer Society, and patient education materials.[27] Wittich et al. reported that frequent exposure to screening via media may increase the probability of acquiring CRC screening.[28]

Conclusion:

The results of this study showed the level of Health Literacy is a predictive factor to evaluate screening behavior in Colorectal Cancer. Therefore, health policymakers and health care providers should consider interventions to increase HL.

It is recommended that large research may be performed to clarify the impact of HL on the adoption of Colorectal Cancer preventive behaviors especially screening Methods. At least, future studies need to clarify which dimensions of HL may also be expecting screening uptake and how it's miles pleasant measured. However, much less than half of the overall populace eligible for CRC screening verified adequate HL that is crucial to remember while communicate with individuals approximately the pros and cons of CRC screening.

Moreover, doctors and health care staff should evaluate the level of HL and based on that level explain everything such as prevention, screening, and treatment approaches.

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